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VOLUME 1

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A QUARTERLY PUBLICATION

- Poetry
- Short Stories
- Essays
- Spotlight on Emerging Writers
- Creative Corner
- Others

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“HAPPY MOTHER’S DAY”

You who were there to help me stand.

Always open to give a helping hand.

Whenever life strangled me along,

You were my guide, happy and strong.

Your light shown to everyone you know.

A presence that gave them confidence to grow.

Someday someone will see me like I see you,

Cause you shaped me to be a reflection of you.

The reason why I've succeeded in life so far
Is because you made me kind, pretty, and smart

I'm very fortunate to have a mom like you.

I wrote this poem to say *I Love You*.